

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Correlating Code Smells and Refactorings in the Elixir functional language

Institutions: DCC/ICEx/UFMG and DPI/CCE/UFV

Responsible researchers:

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Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand developers' perspectives on the ability of refactoring strategies for Elixir to remove code smells from programs implemented in this language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception of code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir (i.e., the completeness of the removals).

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 60 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research or the ethical aspects of this study: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucas.vegi@ufv.br.

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Avançar

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Limpar formulário

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

Select your country: *

Your city: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

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Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Perceptions on code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir

In previous studies, we cataloged [35 code smells](#) and [82 refactorings](#) tailored for Elixir. **In the present work, we are proposing practical guidelines for removing code smells in Elixir using sequences of refactorings specific to the language.**

For each code smell you are asked to evaluate, we will present the refactorings useful for its removal and explain their specific applications. These refactorings are listed in the order in which they should be performed when they are part of a sequence of operations. Specifically, when a refactoring should be applied on its own, it is listed with a bullet point (i.e., •). Conversely, when a refactoring is part of a sequence of operations, it is numbered to indicate its order (e.g., 1., 2., etc.).

Therefore, based on your experience, please answer the following questions for each presented smell:

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings removes this smell?

- Please rate the degree to which the refactoring sequence removes the code smell
- (1 = the refactoring sequence absolutely does not help remove the smell; 5 = the refactoring sequence completely removes the smell)

Notes:

- Each smell and refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link with code examples.

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the **[Inappropriate intimacy]** smell? *

In Elixir, this code smell can be felt in *impure functions*. These functions can access internal values of other modules that are not received via parameters, generating excessive coupling. Particularly, the values accessed by impure functions of a module "A", can be internal details of a module "B", obtained by calling functions of module "B", inside functions of module "A". To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. **[Closure conversion]**: A specific type of Inappropriate intimacy can be seen in closures, which are impure anonymous functions, as they access variables outside their scope. One way to remove this smell is by transforming the closure into a pure anonymous function.
 2. **[Add or remove a parameter]**: Imagine the scenario where an anonymous function A is defined within a named function B. Furthermore, consider that A accesses a variable in its body that is a parameter of B, which is not passed as a parameter to A (i.e., function A is a closure). When applying the previous refactoring to remove the Inappropriate intimacy instance in A, we may end up with unused parameters in the named function B. Therefore, we can use the present refactoring in B to fix it.
- **[Moving a definition]**: If a function in module A is impure because it accesses internal details of module B without receiving them through its parameters, we can remove this smell by moving the function from A to B, thus reducing the coupling between modules.
1. **[Splitting a large module]**: If the modules involved in an instance of this smell have common interests, we can use this refactoring to put their commonality in a new module and make them high-cohesive and low-coupling modules.
 2. **[Rename an identifier]**: In some cases, after splitting an original module into several smaller and more cohesive modules, the name of the original module can no longer make sense, providing an opportunity to also apply this refactoring.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Large messages\]](#) smell? *

When processes exchange messages, their contents are copied between them. For this reason, if a huge structure is sent as a message from one process to another, the sender can become blocked, compromising performance. If these large message exchanges occur frequently, the prolonged and frequent blocking of processes can cause a system to behave anomalously. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Defining a subset of a Map\]](#): If we are originally sending a complete *Map* from one process to another, but actually only need to send a few fields from this *Map*, we can use this refactoring to help reduce the size of the message sent.
- [\[Extract expressions\]](#): When we use *spawn/1* to perform message passing between processes, we can pass an anonymous function as a parameter to *spawn/1* that accesses a *Map* field in its body. This will still copy over all of the *Map*, because the *Map* variable is being captured inside the spawned function. The function then extracts the field, but only after the whole *Map* has been copied over. Suppose we only need to send one field of a *Map* between processes. In that case, we can reduce the size of this message by using this refactoring to store only the necessary value of the *Map* field in a temporary variable. This variable is then used in the spawned function.
- [\[Add a tag to messages\]](#): Optionally, when we are removing this code smell, we may have the opportunity to adapt the processes that communicate with each other by adding tags that identify groups of messages exchanged between them.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Speculative assumptions\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when code makes assumptions that were not planned for, resulting in incorrect return values in situations where a crash would be more appropriate. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter\]](#): This smell arises when developers write defensive or imprecise code, which can return incorrect values that were not planned for. To remove it, we can use this refactoring to force a function to crash instead of returning an invalid value when something unexpected happens.
- [\[Pipeline using "with"\]](#): If this smell occurs within nested conditional statements, we can use this refactoring to remove them. This operation relies on pattern matching to prevent the continuation of tasks that depend on specific data formats.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Speculative generality\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a code has fragments that were implemented in order to give it flexibility in the future, but in practice they end up not being useful because they are never used. In Elixir, this smell can be felt in *modules* not used anywhere in the code, *functions* that are never called or even in functions with *parameters* defined with default values and which do not have calls that inform different values for these parameters. Code with this smell is unnecessarily large and more difficult to maintain. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Inline function\]](#): Use this refactoring to get rid of unused functions or even unnecessarily created ones.
- [\[Inline macro\]](#): Similarly to the previous refactoring, use this operation to eliminate unused macros or those that were unnecessarily created.
- [\[Add or remove a parameter\]](#): Functions with unused parameters should be reviewed using this refactoring.
- [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): Functions with abstract names should be renamed using more specific names that reflect their current task, rather than potential future tasks they might perform.
- [\[Behaviour inlining\]](#): Unnecessary delegation/generalization caused by the excessive use of Elixir's *behaviour* can be removed with this refactoring.
- [\[Remove dead code\]](#): In general, any code created unnecessarily to support future features that are never implemented can be refactored using this operation.
- [\[Eliminate single branch\]](#): When a conditional is created to potentially provide different treatments for different types of data but actually provides the same treatment to all, we can simplify the code by removing unnecessary complexity.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Data manipulation by Migration\]](#) smell? *

This code smell refers to modules that perform both data and structural changes in a database schema via *Ecto.Migration*. Migrations must be used exclusively to modify a database schema over time (e.g., by including or excluding columns and tables). When this responsibility is mixed with data manipulation code, the module becomes less cohesive, more difficult to test, and therefore more prone to bugs. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Splitting a large module\]](#): When a module that behaves like *Ecto.Migration* performs both data and structural changes in a database schema, it becomes less cohesive, more difficult to test, and therefore more prone to bugs. In these cases, we should split this module into two, moving only the attributes and functions related to data updates to the new module.
 2. [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): In some cases, after splitting an original module into several smaller and more cohesive modules, the name of the original module can no longer make sense, providing an opportunity also to perform this refactoring.
 3. [\[Extract function\]](#): We can use this operation in the original module to create a new function responsible for calling the routines for altering the data in the database, now present in the new module.
 4. [\[Moving a definition\]](#): After extracting this function, we can use this refactoring to reposition it in the new module created after splitting the original module.
 5. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): Finally, we can eliminate the call to the extracted function in the original module to start the database alteration routines, as this function, now present in the new module, should only be called during the initialization of a *Mix.Task*.
- [\[Simplifying Ecto schema fields validation\]](#): Optionally, we can take the opportunity to apply this refactoring in the original module, making it less prone to errors during the validation of the database schema modified via *Ecto.Migration*.
 - [\[Pipeline for database transactions\]](#): Optionally, we can also take the opportunity to apply this operation in the new module created only to perform changes on data, thus improving its readability by using *Ecto.Multi*.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Primitive obsession\]](#) smell? *

This code smell can be felt when Elixir basic types (e.g., *integer*, *float*, and *string*) are abusively used in function parameters and code variables, rather than creating specific composite data types (e.g., *protocols*, *structs*, and *@type*) that can better represent a domain. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Grouping parameters in tuple\]](#): If primitive/basic type values are used in function parameters to inadequately represent more complex real-world abstractions, you can initially apply this refactoring to group them.
2. [\[From tuple to struct\]](#): A *tuple* used to group parameters can eventually be replaced by a *struct*, thus creating a more robust data structure for this purpose.

 - [\[Add type declarations and contracts\]](#): We can use this refactoring to generate a type specification to replace primitive/basic values.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Compile-time global configuration\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a function uses module attributes for configuration purposes, thereby preventing run-time configuration. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Extract constant\]](#): To remove this smell caused by using *Application Environment* in compile-time to define module's attributes (i.e., constants), we can perform this refactoring in reverse, that is, perform an *inline* operation.
 - [\[Introduce a temporary duplicate definition\]](#): We can also use this refactoring to create a copy of the compile-time defined constant and replace its definition with a call to *Application.compile_env/3* instead of *Application.fetch_env!/2*.
1. [\[Folding against a function definition\]](#): Another possibility would be to replace the location where a compile-time defined constant is used with a call to the *Application Environment* function responsible for defining the constant's content. This can be done using this refactoring.
 2. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): Finally, if the compile-time defined constant is no longer used in the module, we can simply remove it.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

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Final remarks

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

- Yes
- No

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

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[Enviar](#)

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